

All participants will be recruited by being directly approached by a member of the research team in public and having the study described verbally using the following script:

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Good *[morning/afternoon]*. My name is “[*name*]”, and I am a [Institution Name] research associate working on a research project called “Improving MoMo Payment-Confirmation Interfaces.”

Are you familiar with Mobile Money (MoMo), the way of transferring or receiving money through your phone?

[If yes] Do you use MoMo to send or receive payments?

This project seeks to understand how Rwandans use MoMo with the goal of developing more secure and private interfaces.

Would you be willing to participate in an interview on this topic that lasts 60 minutes? You could complete the interview now or later at a time that is more convenient for you. You will be compensated 7,500 RWF via a MoMo payment for participating. The study asks you questions about your experiences using MoMo, how you verify MoMo payments, and basic demographic information.

- Do you have any questions about the study?
- Are you 18 years of age or older?
- Have you been a resident of Rwanda for at least 5 years?
- Would you like to participate in the study?
- *[if yes]* Great! Would you like to complete the study now or later? We prefer now, but later is ok.
- *[if later]* When would be a good time for you to do so? Would you like to complete the interview on a WhatsApp call or in person?

*[whether or not they are doing the study now or later, we obtain consent in person]*

Before we proceed, we need you to read and complete a consent form.

*[pause for the interviewee to review and sign the consent form.]*

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